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e-mail: marinademidko2302@gmail.com, ORCID 0009-0006-1679-840X**Developing a Sense of Community in the Activities of the University Library of Ukraine in Wartime (on the Example of the Scientific Library of USUST)**

Objective. The authors believe that during the crisis of the highest level, associated with the threat to human life and health, the socio-cultural aspects of the activities of libraries of higher education institutions are important for different countries and require more detailed study. The purpose of the paper is to highlight the practices of developing a sense of community in the socio-cultural activities of a university library in Ukraine in wartime (on the example of the Scientific library of the Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies).

Methods. The article is based on self-reflection, direct experiences and crisis experience of the authors in organising and conducting library leisure activities for students at the Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies (USUST) (Dnipro, Ukraine). The work uses a combination of research approaches and methods: to determine the state of development of the scientific problem, the author used a source search and analysis of relevant publications on the topic of the study; a comparative approach – to compare the similarities and differences in the main functions of university libraries in Ukraine and abroad; the method of observation – to determine the features of various library activities aimed at developing a sense of community among students. **Results.** The crisis experience of wartime librarians demonstrates the ability to quickly replace (despite narrow specialisation in peacetime) and unite colleagues, the ability to integrate cultural and social activities into a single process, simultaneous involvement in various types and forms of professional activities aimed at communities of students, teachers, researchers, and the public. The article presents a fairly wide landscape of leisure practices in the socio-cultural work of the university library of USUST in the frontline city of Dnipro, which allows students, teachers and their children to escape from the already everyday and familiar danger. Librarians help students to restore a sense of unity, cohesion, community, a sense of “I am not alone” and “together we are many”, even when they are often physically separated. **Conclusions.** Community has become a phenomenon that represents Ukrainian spirituality, humanity, dignity and resilience. The activities of university libraries aimed at developing community are especially important for those countries that are experiencing social and political transformations as a result of military conflicts.

Keywords: university library; community; students; crisis experience of librarians; diversity; emotional balance; socio-cultural activity; equity; martial law; Ukraine

Introduction

Informational, educational, scientific, socio-cultural aspects of the activities of libraries of higher education institutions (HEIs), including universities, reflected in the visions, mission, goals, objectives, are derived from the main functions of the institution of which they are a part. These aspects are related not so much to the volume of services provided as to their value (social or personal) and significance for the community (university, academy, institute, college).

Libraries of Ukrainian higher education institutions are designated as special libraries (of academies of sciences, research institutions, educational institutions, etc.) (Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, 1995).

According to the “Model Regulations on the Library of a Higher Education Institution of the Ministry of Education of Ukraine” (Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, 1998), a library of a higher education institution is an educational, scientific, informational, cultural and educational structural unit of a higher education institution. In other words, in addition to

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numerous main tasks of supporting educational activities and research, librarians are also involved in organising certain leisure practices (including cultural leisure) that allow students to escape from their sometimes routine lives, daily academic workload or worries, and contribute to the expansion of knowledge, skills, self-realisation, sense of belonging and sense of community. Of course, the activities of each library have specific features aimed at the mission and strategic goals of the university (academy, institute).

At the same time, according to the IFLA policy, the main function of university libraries is to meet the information needs of teaching and research (International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions, n.d.). For example, the ACRL – Association of College and Research Libraries (2018) of the American Library Association (ALA) focuses on the educational role of such units, stating that “Libraries partner in the educational mission of the institution to develop and support information-literate learners who can discover, access, and use information effectively for academic success, research, and lifelong learning» (Association of College and Research Libraries, 2018). This also applies to collection development: “Libraries provide access to collections sufficient in quality, depth, diversity, format, and currency to support the research and teaching missions of the institution”.

Somewhat different approaches to defining the principles of efficiency of HEI libraries in different countries are due to national peculiarities and socio-cultural situation in the country, region, city.

The authors of this article, having extensive practical and multidisciplinary experience in HEI libraries, consider the university library of Ukraine only in the context of its activities as a cultural and educational unit of the HEI. This unit functions in a certain socio-cultural situation and socio-cultural environment (with its values that have a certain material or spiritual value) that influence the way of behaviour of both users and librarians.

The global crisis caused by the COVID 2019 pandemic has changed living conditions around the world. The so-called “Time of Uncertainty” (Kolesnykova, 2020) dictated significant changes in national higher education for any country, distancing learning and research processes, which also required an urgent communicative reboot of libraries. The rapid introduction, adaptation of librarians to remote work and widespread use of new ICTs by libraries in their activities also made it important to explore ways to strengthen equity, diversity, accessibility, and inclusion in times of uncertainty.

In Ukraine, the deepening of the global crisis as a result of the COVID 2019 pandemic is exacerbated by russia's war of aggression against Ukraine with the intention of seizing its territory, destroying Ukrainians as a nation, its culture, science, and education. Today, the educational process in our country is accompanied by sirens, shelling, and explosions. At the same time, university libraries of Ukraine in the socio-cultural situation of wartime have proved their ability not only to provide information support for learning and research (online and offline). They are involved in the organisation of leisure practices aimed at understanding and active acceptance by Ukrainian students of the values of the democratic world, where an important condition for successful development is the conscious and active involvement of citizens in public life, openness of knowledge, barrier-free access, tolerance, and patriotism.

Literature Review. The directions of deployment of the library's socio-cultural activity in the communication space of the university are quite diverse both in terms of directions and functions: traditional (in particular, informational, cultural, educational), and social (communicative, compensatory, memorial, socialisation, recreational) (Nikolaienko, 2021).

The *Ukrainian Library Encyclopedia* (Ukrainska bibliotechna entsyklopediia, 2024) describes various components of the socio-cultural activities of libraries that can be conducted both offline and online: art and book exhibitions, literary battles, quizzes, literature salons,

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makerspaces, book presentations, readers' conferences, etc. Such a variety of forms and activities is aimed at the free development of users and their involvement in the values of national and world culture.

In 2020, researchers from Erasmus University Rotterdam (Rotterdam, the Netherlands), having conducted informal conversations with undergraduates, found out what happens to students' leisure (including cultural leisure) in the event of extreme scenarios during COVID-19, "when the world becomes the size of our apartments" (Marques & Giolo, 2020). Their conclusions: leisure can still find its way through circumstances, in old and new forms. Students benefit from digital cultural initiatives by artists, museums, libraries, festivals and other cultural agents. The quarantine restrictions have also encouraged various forms of creativity in their leisure time.

Ukrainian researchers from the Scientific Library of the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts (Kyiv, Ukraine) are considering the experience of using digital tools in educational and cultural practices in higher education institutions on the example of cooperation between the Department of Philosophy and the Scientific Library (Gorban & Skachenko, 2020). The gamified form of using the Kahoot digital tool to test students' knowledge of the discipline "Philosophy" was carried out using an online quiz. On the one hand, this is a successfully overcome professional challenge for librarians and teachers, and on the other hand, it is the formation of a sense of belonging to a modern university, teamwork, and community among young people.

Nan Li (Li, 2022) from the Southwest University Library (Chongqing, China) studied the practices of Living book service. The author argues that Living book service enhances cultural communication and educational functions of the library, which brings a new spirit and vitality to the development of librarianship. Living book service not only satisfies the readers' curiosity and enables them to obtain knowledge and experience they need, but also establishes a good relationship of communication and understanding between "Real Person Books" and readers. It resonates by face-to-face discussion of different life experiences, living experiences or beliefs, and it is also an innovation of the traditional library service mode.

Students of colleges/universities in the USA and Ukraine took part in a survey on the development of promising library information mobile services that can be used for leisure practices (Hranchak, Dease, & Lopatovska, 2024). Such services may include access to educational, scientific, popular science, and fiction literature; information and reference services via messengers; development of library mobile applications with audio and video content; and supplementing online services with library chatbots.

In Ukraine, during the highest-level crisis – the Russian-Ukrainian war, an important mobile service (including as a promotion of the unique historical, scientific and cultural heritage) is access to e-copies of engineering retrospectives of 1868-1940 from the collections of the former 2 libraries: of Dnipro National University of Railway Transport and the National Metallurgical Academy of Ukraine (Petrenko & Sidorchuk, 2019). Now, after the reorganisation of the HEI, these libraries are branch structural units of the Scientific Library of the Ukrainian State University of Science and Technology (USUST, Dnipro). As of 01 September 2024, the online collection "Railway Ukrainian Studies" contains 374 copies of such retrospectives (<https://ecat.ust.edu.ua/zu/index.html>), and the online collection "Metallurgical Ukrainian Studies" contains 27 copies of the publications (<https://ecat.ust.edu.ua/met/index.html>).

The involvement of young people in activities to preserve and promote cultural heritage is widespread and important in any country. The participation of Albanian students in the care of library collections, archaeological sites, museums, and local heritage trails not only raises their

awareness of heritage values, but also helps to develop support networks for the preservation and promotion of cultural values (Menkshi, Braholli, Çobani, & Shehu, 2021).

Focusing on democratic values and the UN Sustainable Development Goals in times of uncertainty also has different implications for librarianship, including the development of a sense of community in its activities. An article by researchers from Las Vegas University Libraries (Las Vegas, Nevada, USA) shows that incorporating social justice, diversity, equity and inclusion requires individuals taking action. If institutions want to focus on any of these issues, they need to formally include them in their mission, vision and values as well as in department goals and individual job descriptions (Fiedler, Mitola & Cheng; 2020).

The team of Ukrainian authors from Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University (Uman, Ukraine), Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University (Ivano-Frankivsk, Ukraine) and Vinnytsia Academy of Continuing Education (Vinnytsia, Ukraine) (Bezliudniy et al., 2022) explored the problem of national and patriotic education of students using digital technologies in distance learning. Librarians and teachers describe examples of such activities: thematic online lectures, educational hours, round tables, master classes, online guest meetings with famous researchers of the historical heritage of Ukraine, online excursions to historical sites, virtual art exhibitions, participation in the national-patriotic student camp “Diia”, etc. It is proved that national and patriotic education will be effective if systematic and targeted activities are carried out to form patriotic consciousness, a sense of national dignity, and the need to serve the ideals and values of the country.

The first survey (5-17 May 2022) after the start of the full-scale armed invasion, the authors of which studied the impact of the war on the mental and emotional well-being of Ukrainian civilians – university students and staff – revealed shocking data (Kurapov et al., 2022). According to an online survey of students, faculty and staff of Ukrainian universities who remained in Ukraine, 97.8% of respondents reported a deterioration in their psycho-emotional state, with complaints of depression (84.3%), exhaustion (86.7%), loneliness (51.8%), nervousness (84.4%) and anger (76.9%). Students were more likely than staff to report exhaustion, loneliness, nervousness and anger in the survey, and women were more likely than men to report depression, exhaustion, loneliness and nervousness.

The article by Olha Shkyra, director of the Library of Hryhorii Skovoroda University in Pereiaslav (Ukraine), aims to analyse the poetic experience of amateurs, members of the university community – students, teachers, librarians – as an effective psychotherapeutic method of restoring emotional balance during the full-scale war between Russia and Ukraine (Shkyra, 2022).

Analysis of the world's professional literature shows that the topic of socio-cultural activities is not a trend for most modern libraries of higher education institutions in the world. The ongoing economic crisis, current changes in higher education pedagogy, research, and the production, dissemination, and access to information have all contributed to the need for university libraries to provide new resources and environments that support new pedagogies focused on learning and greater attention to information literacy with a critical approach, as well as active contributions to research impact (Camargo-Rojas, 2024).

However, the authors of this paper believe that during the crisis of the highest level, associated with the threat to human life and health, the socio-cultural aspects of the activities of libraries of higher education institutions are important for different countries and require more detailed study.

The purpose of the paper is to highlight the practices of developing a sense of community in the socio-cultural activities of a university library in Ukraine in wartime (on the example of the Scientific library of the Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies).

Methods

Since the COVID 2019 pandemic and until today, almost a thousand days since the beginning of the full-scale invasion of Ukraine by the Russian Federation, there have been significant changes in the communication practices of the country's higher education libraries. The article examines various forms of deployment of the library's socio-cultural activities during crisis situations in the context of developing a sense of community among students.

The work uses a combination of research approaches and methods: to determine the state of development of the scientific problem, the author used a source search and analysis of relevant publications on the topic of the study; a comparative approach – to compare the similarities and differences in the main functions of university libraries in Ukraine and abroad; the method of observation – to determine the features of various library activities aimed at developing a sense of community among students.

The article is based on self-reflection, direct experiences and crisis experience of the authors in organising and conducting library leisure activities for students at the Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies (USUST) (Dnipro, Ukraine).

Results and Discussion

In today's tragic time for Ukraine, associated with the outbreak of war (2014) and Russia's full-scale invasion of the country (24 February 2022), the crisis experience of Ukrainian librarians in resilience, adaptability, integration, gaining new meanings and changing the social aspect of their activities is especially important.

One of the authors of the article has already described this experience of survival and implementation of new opportunities of the USUST Library to work in times of crisis, which can be extrapolated to other libraries of Ukrainian higher education institutions (Kolesnykova, 2023). Thus, a sharp reduction in the staff of libraries, consisting mainly of women, for various reasons (forced relocation to safe countries, optimisation of HEIs, minimum salary, psychological factors, etc.) has led to a shortage of professional staff and, at the same time, to the urgent adaptation of library staff of Ukrainian HEIs to critical conditions.

Overcoming the unprecedented challenges of a devastating war in the USUST library, for example, includes:

- Changing working conditions in the cold rooms or library halls in winter with a constant temperature of only 6-9 degrees Celsius, as Russian missiles systematically destroy critical infrastructure throughout Ukraine;
- Gaining new meanings: librarians are actively engaged in volunteering in their free time (creating handmade products – warm knitted clothes, trench candles, warm fur belts, etc.), donating blood, transferring their own funds to the needs of the Armed Forces;
- Changes in the social aspect of the activity: librarians support victims who have had traumatic experiences in saving their own lives and the lives of their children. This also applies to internally displaced students under the academic mobility programme, as well as to teachers and other people temporarily residing on campus. According to the Hospitality management model, in all forms of customer service and online and offline events, users are offered to choose the most attractive form of communication: physical or online.

The crisis experience of librarians in developing a sense of community among students.

According to the authors, it is important to note the chance that wartime librarians used 100% – the ability to quickly replace (despite narrow specialisation in peacetime) and unite

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colleagues, the ability to integrate cultural and social activities into a single process, simultaneous involvement in various types and forms of professional activities aimed at communities of students, teachers, researchers, and the public.

This applies, for example, to the crisis experience of USUST librarians in developing a sense of unity, cohesion, and community among students, which, like a “safety belt”, help restore emotional balance, the feeling of “I am not alone” and “together we are many”, even in the face of often forced physical separation.

Considering the sense of community as a synergy of community resources, librarians emphasise, on the one hand, their diversity and multiplicity, and on the other hand, the desire for unity in representing the best features of the national character of Ukrainians: democracy, freedom-loving, tolerance of other peoples, family worship, religiosity, diligence, etc.

The physical separation caused by the COVID 2019 pandemic and the first months of confusion from the incredible and unjustified aggression and atrocities of the Russian army in Ukraine have somewhat dulled the sense of community. Thus, the first months after 24 February 2022 led to a reassessment of values, as the main thing was to save the lives of children, youth, women, and the elderly, and some socio-cultural processes in the country were put on a very short pause. However, in April-May, cultural and educational activities began to intensify, despite the “hot phase” of the war.

The shared experience of the unknown, the test of each Ukrainian's resilience during the war, contributed to the fact that community has become a phenomenon that represents Ukrainian spirituality, humanity and dignity.

It is incredibly important for each person, especially during crisis situations in life, to find their own type of self-expression to preserve themselves and restore emotional balance. That is why the USUST Scientific Library, located in the frontline city of Dnipro, is looking for effective approaches to engage students in activities that strengthen the community (group, faculty, institute, university, region, country) both offline and online. It is important for us to listen carefully to how they react, what they talk about, how they respond, to learn from each other, to understand why young people choose to stand together. This is the only way we will see community.

The peculiarity of the activities of Ukrainian higher education institutions and their libraries in today's wartime is the two-vector nature of their existence: first, the transfer of a significant part of educational and scientific processes to the virtual environment; second, conducting offline training and library events in underground shelters, using digital means, if necessary.

The USUST Scientific Library uses two groups of digital tools to facilitate the implementation of socio-cultural tasks. Firstly, network communication tools – the website of the USUST Scientific Library and the websites of the branch libraries of the institutes that are part of the University; social network accounts, virtual exhibitions, virtual literature review, virtual tours, podcasts, book trailers, digitised library collections, video clips, etc. Secondly, more traditional offline events that use digital technologies.

Online format of library events. In the online environment, the priority of the USUST Library is to form an integral online community of the University through a set of socio-cultural events. The online format of some library events includes video poetry, virtual tours, online quizzes, literary video reviews, online greetings, video clip contests, etc. For example, the following video clips were created and posted on the USUST library's YouTube channel: “Vyshyvanka of USUST 2023” (<http://surl.li/dmoxgs>), video poetry “Destiny” (<http://surl.li/owdcfq>) and “Don't Speak with Sad Eyes” (<http://surl.li/dppqbg>), “We are positive and creative. Ukrainian Positive in Sunshine” (<http://surl.li/qozhfh>), “A winter fairy tale”

(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8oS1RB07qHQ>), “The Day of the Chernobyl Tragedy”
(<http://surl.li/sexlhx>).

Fig. 1. Cultural media project of the Library “Vyshyvanka of USUNT 2023”
(<http://surl.li/dmoxgs>)

The librarians have personally experienced the validity of psychologists' advice that every person, especially in times of crisis, tries to find their own form of self-expression to preserve themselves and restore emotional balance. They sincerely share their knowledge and communication practices with students by organising library events in different physical locations, forms and contexts. According to librarians, the greatest cohesion among young people occurs during the work on the library's video projects, when students act as directors, actors, and decorators, creating a circle of creativity, mutual assistance, and community.

Fig. 2. Cultural media project of the Library “Winter Fairy Tale”
(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8oS1RB07qHQ>)

Offline format of library events. Various locations are used to create zones of creative realisation for amateurs from different circles of the university community – poets, writers, artists, potters, weavers, embroiderers, handicraftsmen and photographers – in physical locations: from the alleys of cherry blossom trees in spring to artists' workshops in winter. Of course, the main target audience is students.

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Safe conditions for both education and socio-cultural events during the war are mandatory. That is why most of the physical library events at USUST are held (in the absence of missile or bomb threats) in the Art Space of the branch library of the USUST Educational and Research Institute. But at the first air raid alarm, all participants move to underground shelters. That is why such socio-cultural events in the physical spaces of USUST branch libraries are characterised by intimacy and a relatively small (up to 40 people) number of participants.

For example, the components of a large and diverse set of events are:

- “Literary meetings” – for fans of the creative word. At the meetings, authors' works of both students and graduates, including many soldiers of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, are read. The experience of amateur poetry, born out of pain, love, suffering, care, and tears of joy, helps participants realise the importance of expressing their feelings in a circle of like-minded people;
- As part of the National Poetry Week “Rivers Always Flow Home” – poem recitation by students, including IDPs from the russian-occupied territories who have lost their homes. Poems by classics and contemporaries – T. Shevchenko, L. Kostenko, V. Stus, Y. Andrukhovych, S. Zhadan, P. Vyshebababa, and other poets – performed by girls and boys evoke different memories and emotions that seem to be lived by young people and at the same time give them hope for the best;
- Interactive event “Things from Grandma's Chest: Headscarf as a type of headdress for Ukrainian women”. In the context of local history, with elements of training, games, and folk music, students learned about the main types of headscarves that existed in Ukraine in different historical periods, the differences between local and foreign-made headscarves, and revealed the secrets of popular ways of tying headscarves in the Prydniprovie region;
- Exhibition of drawings “Ukraine will win. We thank the Armed Forces of Ukraine”. The artists include students and children of employees. Such amateur youth exhibitions, often the first in their lives, have a future, because the strength of Ukrainians is in unity, cohesion and loyalty to their country, and now we understand this more than ever;

Fig. 3. A collection of drawings “Artfight in my life” by student Zabava Chorna (Photo by Maryna Demidko)

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- Workshops “Creativity for Victory”. Masters (teachers and librarians) taught students various handmade techniques. For example, how to turn a used military item – a shell casing – into a real work of art, or how to create a motanka doll for the Ukrainian Armed Forces; or how to paint an Easter egg for the Easter holiday. Whatever the students created at the workshops, they put a piece of their soul and positive attitude into each of them as an opportunity to convey their support and care to the guys and girls at the front.
- Psychological trainings are conducted by practical psychologists. For example, the “Vision Board” training. A vision board is a visual image of what we dream about. As always, in a wonderful friendly atmosphere, our students visualised goals in all areas that can change their lives for the better. After all, it is only through balance and harmony in life that we can achieve what we want.

Fig. 4. Student visualisation of the “Vision Board” (Photo by Maryna Demidko)

- The PlayDay board game space is a leisure support and library shelter where students can gather, get to know each other, and help each other realise their potential. Favourite team psychological games are Bunker, Mafia, etc.
- Patriotic meetings with veterans of the Russian-Ukrainian war, military and clergy, trips to numerous museums in Dnipro and exploring the city's historical sights. The heroes of the meetings discuss simple truths with the students, such as that love for God, for one's family, for nature, for the Motherland with its culture and traditions necessarily makes every person want to protect all of this. This is patriotism as a value, which is the driving force behind the defence of our native Ukraine.
- Radio Dictation of National Unity, which took place on 25 October 2024 in various locations: libraries, classrooms, shelters, at home in front of a computer... This year's radio dictation was held for the 25th time and for the third time in the context of the great war. The purpose of the annual dictation is to unite Ukrainians around the world in their love for the Ukrainian word and language learning.

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This, in our opinion, is a fairly broad landscape of leisure practices in the socio-cultural work of the USUST University Library in the frontline city of Dnipro, which enables students, teachers and their children to escape the already everyday and familiar danger (no matter how tragic and strange it may sound). Such practices also contribute to the expansion of knowledge, skills, enthusiasm, a sense of belonging to the community and self-realisation. Librarians help students to restore a sense of unity, cohesion, community, a sense of “I am not alone” and “together we are many”, even when they are often physically separated.

And librarians themselves have managed to find new meaning in their work in a time of crisis, as they have focused on helping others through new, targeted activities that motivate and enjoy, reassure and empower, and provide at least some sense of stability and normalcy amidst the chaos of war.

In addition, librarians record the highlights of each event (reports, photos, news on the library's website, feedback from participants, social media posts). They are and will be the keepers of memories who will lead the promotion of any wartime student creativity. A special kind of creativity, born out of uncertainty and loneliness, care and love, anger and shame, joy and mercy, irritation and anger, cheerfulness and hope...

Conclusions

The study of the conditions and practices for developing a sense of community in the socio-cultural activities of the university library of Ukraine in wartime on the experience of the Scientific library of the Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies allowed drawing certain conclusions.

The activities of university libraries aimed at developing community are especially important for those countries that are experiencing social and political transformations as a result of military conflicts. Significant human losses, a decrease in the number of students in the country, relocation of teachers, researchers and staff to safer regions of the country or abroad, attention to inclusion and diversity – this is only an incomplete list of the consequences of the impact of war on higher education in any country. Ukraine, unfortunately, has such a tragic experience.

The authors believe that somewhat different approaches to defining the principles of efficiency of HEI libraries in different countries are due not only to the focus on supporting and performing the main functions of the institution. The issue of the socio-cultural situation and the socio-cultural environment in the country, region, city, which influence the way of behaviour of both users and librarians themselves, plays a major role.

In the socio-cultural situation of wartime, Ukrainian librarians actively demonstrate the ability to quickly replace colleagues (despite narrow specialisation in peacetime) and unite, the ability to integrate cultural and social activities into a single process, and simultaneous engagement in various types and forms of professional activities aimed at communities of students, teachers, researchers, and the public.

University life is built on the synergy of students, teachers and staff in the academic community of university campuses. The disruption of the sense of belonging and the university's identity values due to the restrictions on physical communication during the COVID 2019 pandemic and the ongoing full-scale Russian-Ukrainian war has also affected the sense of community.

Considering the sense of community as a synergy of community resources, librarians emphasise, on the one hand, their diversity and multiplicity, and on the other hand, the desire for

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unity in representing the best features of the national character of Ukrainians: democracy, freedom-loving, tolerance of other peoples, family worship, religiosity, diligence, etc.

The shared experience of the unknown by the libraries of Ukrainian higher education institutions and, in particular, the USUST Scientific Library, and the test of each Ukrainian for resilience during the war, have contributed to the fact that community has become a phenomenon that represents Ukrainian spirituality, humanity, dignity, resilience and perhaps a model of life that will actively influence the future of the country.

According to the USUST librarians, a great cohesion of young people arises during the work on the library's video projects (video poetry, video performances, videos with folk rituals, dance videos), when students act in different roles – directors, actors, decorators, stylists, creating a circle of creativity, mutual assistance, and the sense of community.

The experience of the USUST Library, gained during a crisis of the highest level – an armed conflict (war), proves that students' sense of community is most effectively formed in a relatively small physical space. The intimacy of the event (30-40 people), a sense of security, live feedback, tea and cakes, costumes and Ukrainian rituals, close discussions, and collective reasoning create a kind of field of community, teamwork, responsibility, patriotism, cultural uplift, and mutual understanding. It is in this intimacy that the community experiences different emotions within itself.

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Розвиток почуття спільності в діяльності університетської бібліотеки України воєнного часу (на прикладі наукової бібліотеки УДУНТ)

Мета. Автори вважають, що під час кризи найвищого рівня, пов'язаною із загрозою життю і здоров'ю людей, соціокультурні аспекти діяльності бібліотек закладів вищої освіти є важливим для різних країн і потребують більш детального вивчення. Метою статті є висвітлення практик із розвитку почуття спільності в соціокультурній діяльності університетської бібліотеки України воєнного часу (на прикладі Наукової бібліотеки Українського державного університету науки і технологій). **Методика.** Стаття базується на саморефлексії, безпосередніх переживаннях і кризовому досвіді авторок в організації і проведенні бібліотечних дозвілєвих заходів для студентів Українського державного університету науки і технологій (УДУНТ) (Дніпро, Україна). В роботі застосовано сукупність дослідницьких підходів і методів: для з'ясування стану розробленості наукової проблеми використано джерелознавчий пошук і аналіз профільних публікацій з теми дослідження; компаративний підхід – для порівняння спільного і відмінного в українських і зарубіжних основних функціях університетських бібліотек; метод спостереження – для з'ясування особливостей різноформатних бібліотечних заходів із розвитку у студентів почуття спільності. **Результати.** Кризовий досвід бібліотекарів воєнного часу демонструє здатність до швидкої взаємозамінності колег (незважаючи на вузьку спеціалізацію в мирні роки) і об'єднання, можливість інтегрувати культурні та соціальні заходи в єдиний процес, одночасна задіяність в різних видах і формах професійної діяльності, спрямованій на спільноти студентів, викладачів, дослідників, громадськість. Представлено досить широкий ландшафт дозвілєвих практик у соціокультурній роботі університетської бібліотеки УДУНТ у прифронтовому місті Дніпро, який дає можливість студентам, викладачам та їхнім дітям відволіктися від уже повсякденної та звичної небезпеки. Бібліотекарі сприяють відновленню у студентів почуття єдності, згуртованості, спільності, відчуття “я не один” і “разом нас багато”, навіть при часто вимушеній фізичній відокремленості. **Висновки.** Спільнотність стала явищем, яке репрезентує українську духовність, людяність, гідність та стійкість. Заходи бібліотек ЗВО, спрямовані на розвиток спільності, є особливо важливими для тих країн, які переживають соціальні та політичні трансформації внаслідок військових конфліктів.

Ключові слова: університетська бібліотека; спільнотність; студенти; кризовий досвід бібліотекарів; різноманітність; емоційна рівновага; соціокультурна діяльність; справедливість; воєнний стан; Україна

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